

RG η -Closed Sets in Topological Spaces

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Abstract: In this paper, a new class of sets called regular generalized η -closed (briefly $rg\eta$ -closed) sets is introduced and its properties are studied. The relationships among closed, α -closed, s -closed, η -closed, $rg\eta$ -closed and their generalized closed sets are investigated. Several examples are provided to illustrate the behavior of these new class of sets.

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1. Introduction

Many investigations related to generalized closed sets have been published in various forms of closed sets. In 1937, Stone [12] introduced the notion of regular open sets. In 1963, Levine [7] introduced the concept of semi-open sets. In 1965, Njastad [11] introduced the concept of α -open sets. In 1968, the notion of π -open sets were introduced by Zaitsev [16] which are weaker form of regular open sets in topological spaces. In 1970, Levine [8] initiated the study of so called generalized closed (briefly g -closed) sets. In 1994, Maki et al. [9, 10] introduced the notion of αg -closed sets. In 2000, Dontchev and Noiri [4] introduced the notion of πg -closed sets. In 2007, Arockiarani and Janaki [2] introduced the notion of $\pi g\alpha$ -closed sets in topological spaces. In 2019, Subbulakshmi, Sumathi, Indirani [14, 15] introduced and investigated the notion of η -open and $g\eta$ -closed sets. In 2019, Kumar and Sharma [5] introduced and investigated the notion of η - T_k ($k = 0, 1, 2$) and η - R_k ($k = 0, 1, 2$) axioms in topological spaces. Recently, Kumar [6] introduced and investigated the notion of $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $cl(A)$ and $int(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** [12] (resp. **regular closed** [12]) if $A = int(cl(A))$ (resp. $A = cl(int(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open** [16]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed** [16].

Definition 2.1. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (i) **s -open** [7] if $A \subset cl(int(A))$.
- (ii) **α -open** [11] if $A \subset int(cl(int(A)))$.
- (iii) **η -open** [14] if $A \subset in(cl(int(A))) \cup cl(int(A))$.
- (iv) **η -closed** [14] if $A \supset cl(int(cl(A))) \cup int(cl(A))$.

The complement of a s -open (resp. α -open, η -open) set is called **s -closed** (resp. **α -closed**, **η -closed**). The intersection

of all s -closed (resp. α -closed, η -closed) sets containing A , is called **s -closure** (resp. **α -closure**, **η -closure**) of A , and is denoted by **$s-cl(A)$** (resp. **$\alpha-cl(A)$** , **$\eta-cl(A)$**). The **η -interior** of A , denoted by **$\eta-int(A)$** is defined as union of all η -open sets contained in A . We denote the family of all η -open (resp. η -closed) sets of a topological space by **$\eta-O(X)$** (resp. **$\eta-C(X)$**).

Definition 2.2. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

- (1) **generalized closed** (briefly **g -closed**) [8] if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (2) **πg -closed** [4] if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (3) **rg -closed** [4] if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .
- (4) **α -generalized closed** (briefly **αg -closed**) [9, 10] if $\alpha-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (5) **$\pi g\alpha$ -closed** [2] if $\alpha-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (6) **gar -closed** [13] if $\alpha-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .
- (7) **generalized semi-closed** (briefly **gs -closed**) [1] if $s-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (8) **πgs -closed** [3] if $s-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .
- (9) **rgs -closed** if $s-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .
- (10) **generalized η -closed** (briefly **$g\eta$ -closed**) [15] if $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.
- (11) **$\pi g\eta$ -closed** (briefly **$g\eta$ -closed**) [6] if $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and is π -open in X .
- (12) **g -open** (resp. **πg -open**, **rg -open**, **αg -open**, **$\pi g\alpha$ -open**, **gar -open**, **gs -open**, **πgs -open**, **rgs -open**, **$g\eta$ -open**, **$\pi g\eta$ -open**) set if the complement of A is g -closed (resp. πg -closed, rg -closed, αg -closed, $\pi g\alpha$ -closed, gar -closed, gs -closed, πgs -closed, rgs -closed, $g\eta$ -closed, $\pi g\eta$ -closed).

3. Regular Generalized η -closed Sets

Definition 3.1. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **regular generalized η -closed** (briefly **$rg\eta$ -closed**) if $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X . The family of all $rg\eta$ -closed subsets of X will be denoted by

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$rg\eta$ -C(X).

Theorem 3.2. Every closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.

Proof. Let A be a closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is closed, that is, $cl(A) = A$, $cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

Theorem 3.3. For a topological space X the followings hold:

- (1) Every g-closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (2) Every πg -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (3) Every rg-closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (4) Every α -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (5) Every αg -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (6) Every $\pi g\alpha$ -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (7) Every $g\alpha$ -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (8) Every s-closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (9) Every gs-closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (10) Every πgs -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (11) Every rgs-closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (12) Every η -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (13) Every $g\eta$ -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.
- (14) Every $\pi g\eta$ -closed set is $rg\eta$ -closed.

Proof.

(1) Let A be a g-closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is open and since A is g-closed, that is, $cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(2) Let A be a πg -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is π -open and since A is πg -closed, that is, $cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(3) Let A be a rg-closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is rg-closed, that is, $cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(4) Let A be a α -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is α -closed, that is, $\alpha-cl(A) = A$, $\alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset \alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(5) Let A be a αg -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is open and since A is αg -closed, that is, $\alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset \alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(6) Let A be a $\pi g\alpha$ -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is π -open and since A is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed, that is, $\alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset \alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(7) Let A be a $g\alpha$ -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is $g\alpha$ -closed, that is, $\alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset \alpha-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(8) Let A be a s-closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is s-closed, that is, $s-cl(A) = A$, $s-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset s-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(9) Let A be a gs-closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is open and since A is gs-closed, that is, $s-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset s-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(10) Let A be a πgs -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is π -open and since A is πgs -closed, that is, $s-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset s-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(11) Let A be a rgs-closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is rgs-closed, that is, $s-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset s-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(12) Let A be a η -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since A is η -closed, that is, $\eta-cl(A) = A$, $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(13) Let A be a $g\eta$ -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is open and since A is $g\eta$ -closed, that is, $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

(14) Let A be a $\pi g\eta$ -closed set in X. Let U be a regular open set in X such that $A \subset U$. Since every regular open set is π -open and since A is $\pi g\eta$ -closed, that is, $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. But we have $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta-cl(A) \subset U$. Hence A is $rg\eta$ -closed in X.

Remark 3.4: From the above definitions, theorems and known results the relationship between $rg\eta$ -closed sets and some other existing generalized closed sets are implemented in the following figure:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

Example 3.5: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b, c\}$ and $B = \{a, b, d\}$ are πg -closed as well as $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets. A and B are also $rg\eta$ -closed sets but not closed.

Example 3.6: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi g\eta$ -closed. It is also $rg\eta$ -closed set. But it is neither closed nor g -closed. It is not πg -closed.

Example 3.7: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is g -closed, αg -closed, $g\eta$ -closed, $\pi g\alpha$ -closed, $\pi g\eta$ -closed. It is also $rg\eta$ -closed set. But it is not closed.

Example 3.8: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is $\pi g\alpha$ -closed as well as $\pi g\eta$ -closed. It is also $rg\eta$ -closed set. But it is neither closed nor αg -closed set.

Example 3.9: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is η -closed as well as $\pi g\eta$ -closed. It is also $rg\eta$ -closed set. But it not α -closed.

Example 3.10: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is $g\eta$ -closed as well as $\pi g\eta$ -closed. It is also $rg\eta$ -closed set. But it is not closed.

Example 3.11: Let $X = \{0, 1\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{0\}, X\}$. The topological space (X, \mathfrak{S}) is called the Sierpinski space. Then the set $A = \{0\}$ rg -closed as well as $rg\eta$ -closed sets but not closed.

Example 3.12. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, X\}$. Then

- 1) η -closed sets are $\phi, \{e\}, \{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{c, d, e\}$ X .
- 2) $g\eta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{e\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, e\}, \{b, e\}, \{c, d\}, \{c, e\}, \{d, e\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{a, c, e\}, \{a, d, e\}, \{b, c, e\}, \{b, d, e\}, \{c, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, e\}, \{a, b, d, e\}, \{a, c, d, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}, X$.
- 3) $\pi g\eta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{e\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, e\}, \{b, e\}, \{c, d\}, \{c, e\}, \{d, e\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{a, c, e\}, \{a, d, e\}, \{b, c, e\}, \{b, d, e\}, \{c, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, e\}, \{a, b, d, e\}, \{a, c, d, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}, X$.
- 4) $rg\eta$ -closed sets are $\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{e\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{a, e\}, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{b, e\}, \{c, d\}, \{c, e\}, \{d, e\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, \{a, b, e\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, c, e\}, \{a, d, e\}, \{b, c, d\}, \{b, c, e\}, \{b, d, e\}, \{c, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, d\}, \{a, b, c, e\}, \{a, b, d, e\}, \{a, c, d, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}, X$.

4. Characteristics of $rg\eta$ -Closed Sets

Theorem 4.1: If A is regular open and $rg\eta$ -closed, then A is η -closed and hence clopen.

Proof: If A is regular open and $\pi g\eta$ -closed, then $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset A$. This implies A is η -closed. Hence A is clopen, since every η -closed (regular) open set is (regular) closed.

Theorem 4.2: If A and B are $rg\eta$ -closed sets in X then $A \cup B$ is an $rg\eta$ -closed set in X .

Proof: Let A and B be $rg\eta$ -closed sets in X and U be any regular open set containing A and B . Therefore $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$, $\eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$. Since $A \subset U$, $B \subset U$ then $A \cup B \subset U$. Hence $\eta\text{-cl}(A \cup B) = \eta\text{-cl}(A) \cup \eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$. Therefore $A \cup B$ is $rg\eta$ -closed set in X .

Theorem 4.3: A set A is $rg\eta$ -closed set iff $\eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$ contains no non-empty regular closed set.

Proof: Necessity: Let F be a regular closed set in X such that $F \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Then $A \subset X - F$. Since A is an $rg\eta$ -closed set and $X - F$ is regular open then $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset X - F$. (i.e $F \subset X - \eta\text{-cl}(A)$). Then $F \subset (X - \eta\text{-cl}(A)) \cap \eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$. Therefore $F = \phi$.

Sufficiency: Let us assume that $\eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$ contains no non empty regular closed set. Let $A \subset U$ and U be regular-open. Suppose that $\eta\text{-cl}(A)$ is not contained in U , then $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \cap U^c$ is non empty regular closed set of $\eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$ which is a contradiction. Therefore $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$. Hence A is an $rg\eta$ -closed set.

Theorem 4.4: The intersection of any two subsets of $rg\eta$ -closed sets in X is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X .

Proof: Let A and B be two subsets of a $rg\eta$ -closed set. Assume $A, B \subset U$, where U is regular-open. Then $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$, $\eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$. Therefore $\eta\text{-cl}(A \cap B) \subset U$. Since A and B are $rg\eta$ -closed sets, $A \cap B$ is a $rg\eta$ -closed set.

Theorem 4.5: If A is an $g\eta$ -closed set in X and $A \subset B \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A)$, then B is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X .

Proof: Since $B \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A)$, we have $\eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A)$ then $\eta\text{-cl}(B) - B \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$. By **Theorem 3.2**, $\eta\text{-cl}(A) - A$ contains no non empty regular closed set. Hence $\eta\text{-cl}(B) - B$ contains no non empty regular closed set. Therefore B is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X .

Theorem 4.6: Let $A \subset Y \subset X$ be a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X . Then A is a $rg\eta$ -closed set relative to Y .

Proof: Give that $A \subset Y \subset X$ and A is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X . To prove that A is a $rg\eta$ -closed set relative to Y , let us assume that $A \subset Y \cap U$, where U is regular open in X . Since A is an $rg\eta$ -closed set, $A \subset U$ implies $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$. It follows that $Y \cap \eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset Y \cap U$. That is A is a $rg\eta$ -closed set relative to Y .

Theorem 4.7: If A is both regular open and $rg\eta$ -closed set in X then A is a regular closed set.

Proof: Since A is a regular open and $rg\eta$ -closed set in X , $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$. But $A \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A)$. Therefore $A = \eta\text{-cl}(A)$. Therefore A is a regular closed set.

Theorem 4.8: For $x \in X$, the set $X - \{x\}$ is $rg\eta$ -closed or regular open.

Proof: Suppose that $X - \{x\}$ is not regular open, then X is the only regular open set containing $X - \{x\}$. (i.e. $\eta\text{-cl}(X - \{x\}) \subset X$). Then $X - \{x\}$ is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X .

Definition 4.9: Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space, $A \subset X$ and $x \in X$. Then x is said to be a **η -limit point** of A iff every η -open set containing x contains a point of A different from x , and the set of all η -limit points of A is said to be the η -derived set of A and is denoted by $D_\eta(A)$.

Usual derived set of A is denoted by $D(A)$.

The proof of the following result is analogous to the well known ones.

Lemma 4.10: Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space and $A \subset X$. Then $\eta\text{-cl}(A) = A \cup D_\eta(A)$.

Theorem 4.11: Let A and B be $rg\eta$ -closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $D(A) \subset D_\eta(A)$ and $D(B) \subset D_\eta(B)$. Then $A \cup B$ is $rg\eta$ -closed.

Proof: For any set $E \subset (X, \mathfrak{T})$, $D_\eta(E) \subset D(E)$. Therefore $D_\eta(A) = D(A)$ and $D_\eta(B) = D(B)$. That is $\text{cl}(A) = \eta\text{-cl}(A)$ and $\text{cl}(B) = \eta\text{-cl}(B)$.

Let $A \cup B \subset U$ where U is regular open. Then $A \subset U$ and $B \subset U$. Since A and B $rg\eta$ -closed $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$ and $\eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$. Now, $\text{cl}(A \cup B) = \text{cl}(A) \cup \text{cl}(B) = \eta\text{-cl}(A) \cup \eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$. But $\eta\text{-cl}(A \cup B) \subset \text{cl}(A \cup B)$. So $\eta\text{-cl}(A \cup B) \subset U$ and hence $A \cup B$ is $rg\eta$ -closed.

Theorem 4.12: If A is $rg\eta$ -closed and B is any set $A \subset B \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A)$, then B is $rg\eta$ -closed.

Proof: Let $B \subset U$ where U is regular open. Then $A \subset B$ implies $A \subset U$. Since A is $rg\eta$ -closed, $\eta\text{-cl}(A) \subset U$. $B \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A)$ implies $\eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset \eta\text{-cl}(A)$. Thus $\eta\text{-cl}(B) \subset U$ and shows that B is $rg\eta$ -closed.

Regular Generalized η -open Sets and Regular Generalized η -Neighbourhoods

In this section new class of sets called regular generalized η -open (briefly $rg\eta$ -open) sets and regular generalized η -neighbourhoods (briefly $rg\eta$ -nhd) in topological spaces are introduced and we study some of their properties.

Definition 5.1: Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space. A subset A of X is called **regular generalized η -open** (briefly **$rg\eta$ -open**) iff its complement is $rg\eta$ -closed set. We denote the family of all $rg\eta$ -open sets of a topological space by **$rg\eta\text{-O}(X)$** .

Theorem 5.2: If A and B are $rg\eta$ -open sets in a space X , then $A \cup B$ is also a $rg\eta$ -open set in X .

Proof: If A and B are $rg\eta$ -open sets in a space X , then A^c and B^c are $rg\eta$ -closed sets in X . By **Theorem 3.1** $A^c \cup B^c$ is

a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X (i.e. $A^c \cup B^c = (A \cap B)^c$ is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X). Therefore $A \cup B$ is a $rg\eta$ -open set in X .

Remark 5.3: The union of two $rg\eta$ -open sets in X is generally not a $rg\eta$ -open set in X .

Example 5.4: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. The set $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{b\}$ are $rg\eta$ -open sets but $A \cup B = \{a, b\}$ is not a $rg\eta$ -open set in X .

Remark 5.5: If A and B are $rg\eta$ -open sets in X , then $A \cap B$ is not a $rg\eta$ -open set in X .

Example 5.6: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. The set $A = \{a, c\}$ and $B = \{b, c\}$ are $rg\eta$ -open sets but $A \cap B = \{c\}$ is not a $rg\eta$ -open set in X .

Theorem 5.7: If $\text{int}(B) \subset B \subset A$ and A is $rg\eta$ -open set in X , then B is $rg\eta$ -open in X .

Proof: Suppose that $\text{int}(B) \subset B \subset A$ and A is $rg\eta$ -open in X then $A^c \subset B^c \subset A^c$. Since A^c is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X by **Theorem 5.2**, B^c is a $rg\eta$ -closed set in X .

Definition 5.8: Let x be a point in a topological space X . A subset N of X is said to be a **$rg\eta$ -nhd** of x iff there exists a $rg\eta$ -open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$.

Definition 5.9: A subset N of space X is called a **$rg\eta$ -nhd** of $A \subset X$ iff there exists a $rg\eta$ -open set G such that $A \subset G \subset N$.

Theorem 5.10: Every nhd N of $x \in X$ is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of x .

Proof: Let N be a nhd point of $x \in X$. To prove that N is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of x , by definition of nhd, there exists an open set G such that $x \in G \subset N$. Hence N is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of x .

Remark 5.11: In general, a $rg\eta$ -nhd of $x \in X$ need not be a nhd of $x \in X$ as seen from the following example.

Example 5.12: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T} = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. Then $rg\eta\text{-O}(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. The set $\{a, c\}$ is $rg\eta$ -nhd of point b , since the $rg\eta$ -open set $\{b\}$ is such that $b \in \{b\} \subset \{a, b\}$. However, the set $\{a, b\}$ is not a nhd of the point b , since no open set G exists such that $b \in G \subset \{a, c\}$.

Remark 5.13: The $rg\eta$ -nhd N of $x \in X$ need not be a $rg\eta$ -open in X .

Example 5.14: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T} = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. Then $rg\eta\text{-O}(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. The set $\{c\}$ is a $rg\eta$ -open set, but it is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of $\{c\}$. Since $\{c\}$ is a $rg\eta$ -open set such that $c \in \{c\} \subset \{b, c\}$.

Theorem 5.15: If a subset N of a space X is $rg\eta$ -open, then N is $rg\eta$ -nhd of each of all its points.

Proof: Suppose N is $rg\eta$ -open. Let $x \in N$ be an arbitrary point. We claim that N is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of x . Since N is a $rg\eta$ -open set and $x \in N \subset N$, it follows that N is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of all of its points.

Remark 5.16: In general, a $rg\eta$ -nhd of $x \in X$ need not be a nhd of $x \in X$ as seen from the following example.

Example 5.17: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with $\mathfrak{T} = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. Then $rg\eta$ -O(X) = $\{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}\}$. The set $\{a, b\}$ is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of b , since the $rg\eta$ -open set $\{b\}$ is such that $b \in \{b\} \subset \{a, b\}$. Also the set $\{a, b\}$ is a $rg\eta$ -nhd point of $\{b\}$, since the $rg\eta$ -open set $\{b\}$ is such that $b \in \{b\} \subset \{a, b\}$. (i.e. $\{a, b\}$ is a $rg\eta$ -nhd of each of its points). However the set $\{a, b\}$ is not a $rg\eta$ -open set in X .

Theorem 5.18: Let X be a topological space. If F is a $rg\eta$ -closed subset of X and $x \in F^c$ then there exists a $rg\eta$ -nhd N of x such that $N \cap F = \phi$.

Proof: Let X be a $rg\eta$ -closed subset of X and $x \in F^c$. Then F^c is a $rg\eta$ -open set of X . So by **Theorem 5.15** F^c contains a $rg\eta$ -nhd of each of its points. Hence there exists a $rg\eta$ -nhd N of x such that $N \cap F^c = \phi$. (i.e $N \cap F = \phi$).

5. Conclusion

The regular generalized η -closed set is defined and proved that the class forms a topology. The $rg\eta$ -closed set can be used to derive a new decomposition of unity, closed map and open map, homeomorphism, closure and interior and new separation axioms. This idea can be extended to bitopological and fuzzy topological spaces.

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